

TEMA V

NEUROLOŠKA REHABILITACIJA (NOVE TEHNOLOGIJE U REHABILITACIJI)

Predavanje po pozivu

REVIEW OF NOVEL METHODS AND INSTRUMENTATION FOR ASSESSMENT OF SENSORY - MOTOR FUNCTION IN REHABILITATION

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Summary: There is a growing interest in novel rehabilitation strategies which is closely related to rapid technological development. In order to apply optimal and effective therapies, objective assessment procedures are a must. This paper deals with the assessment of sensory-motor function by the means of electromyography. Novel instrumentation, processing methods, and protocols have been proposed and presented in this paper for the assessment of both voluntary muscle contraction and evoked potentials. The advancements such as muscle cocontraction parameters for assessment of muscle activation patterns and application of matrix electrodes for both electrical stimulation and recording of evoked potentials have been surveyed. The recommendations for future directions for development and application of assessment procedures are given in conjunction with already existing protocols.

Key words: muscle assessment, polomyography, evoked potential, matrix electrode, sensory-motor recovery

1 Introduction

The search for the most appropriate and effective therapy is one of the most challenging topics in neurorehabilitation [1]. In order to study the effects of various treatments, one must have in mind appropriate assessment methods. Various clinical scores have been proposed and are used in every-day clinical practice (e.g. Fugl-Meyer score, Berg Balance score, Ashworth scale, Beck depression scale, Oswestry scale, etc.). Though, the repeatability and reproducibility of these scores have been quite satisfactory, their main disadvantage is that they are descriptive and subjective [2-3]. In order to use objective scores in addition to standard clinical scores, researchers have proposed kinetic, kinematic and dynamic measurements of physical performance [4]. In this paper, the objective assessment procedure for studying sensory-motor recovery based on the electromyography is presented.

Electromyography is a method for measurement and analysis of electrical potentials originating from skeletal muscles. Two main approaches have been used for measurements and analysis of EMG signals with the aim of therapy assessment. The first approach is used for studying voluntary muscle contractions in patients compared to healthy-matched controls. Long-term and short-term effects have been studied using this approach and they are mainly focused on studying muscle activation patterns by electromyography (EMG) measurements from various muscle groups [2-3]. The most commonly introduced parameters from single muscle EMG signal reflect amplitude, temporal, and frequency related changes to the specified task. This task is usually related to a significant movement: e.g. in stroke patients two main concerns during recovery of lower extremities are dorsiflexion (single voluntary movement [3]), and gait [2].

The second approach is related to generation, measurement, and analysis of evoked potentials. Most commonly recorded evoked potential in human body is *soleus* H-reflex. Though it is relatively easy to analyze recorded signal due to its deterministic nature, there are numerous difficulties for the clinical application. There is no standardized procedure for placement of stimulation electrodes and for current tuning during electrical stimulation of *tibial* nerve that should produce H-reflex on muscle *soleus*, and there are various factors influencing the nerve excitability [5]. Though, *soleus* muscle H-reflex is relatively easy to generate compared to H-reflex in other muscles, the placement of recording electrodes is not trivial due to the anatomy (relatively small amount of *soleus* muscle fibers is superficial and appropriately reachable by surface electrodes). In order to overcome some of the restrictions, new control algorithms with the application of matrix stimulation and matrix recording electrodes have been proposed [6-7].

In this paper, two main approaches have been proposed as a future directions in electromyography based assessment induced by technological development and technical improvements: 1) the use of polymyography measurements with the proposed parameters corresponding to muscle coactivation; and 2) matrix electrodes application in H-reflex measurements.

2 Review of existing methods and results

2.1 Assessment of voluntary muscle contraction

In order to assess muscle activation pattern, the adequate recording equipment is a must. In [1], the authors have presented a portable instrumentation for recording voluntary muscle contraction from various

muscles in combination with signals from other sensors (e.g. goniometers, and accelerometers).

Figure 1, Muscle cocontractions in one stroke patient during gait. TA (*tibialis anterior*), LG (*lateral gastrocnemius*), RF (*rectus femoris*), and BF (*biceps femoris*) cocontractions are presented. The colored area corresponds to individual muscle contribution to overall movement in non paretic and in paretic leg. Image is adopted from [2].

This instrumentation was used for muscle activation pattern assessment of dorsiflexion in stroke patients [3], and for gait assessment in stroke patients [2]. The assessment was based on the introduced measurements of muscle cocontraction that enabled easier visualization and studying EMG amplitude distribution from various muscles, Fig. 1. This measures are easy-to-use, descriptive and it is shown that they might be used in assessment in stroke patients [2-3].

Figure 2, Matrix electrode interface for recording evoked potentials with corresponding topography map in healthy subject is presented. Pads marked with red color on left panel correspond to signals presented on the right. Color coded amplitude modulation is presented in topography map.

2.1 Assessment of evoked potentials

Recently, in [6-7] novel instrumentation for generation and visualization of human H-reflex was presented. The instrumentation comprises: electrical stimulator, EMG amplifier, PC based controller, matrix recording electrode, and matrix cathode for stimulation of *tibial* nerve. The visualization technique is based on spline interpolation of evoked potential and presented in the form of topography map, Fig. 2. This instrumentation enabled: automatic optimal pad selection for stimulation of *tibial* nerve, automatic optimal pad selection for recording H-reflex, automatic optimal current tuning, and studying the spatial amplitude/latency distribution of the H-reflex over recorded area by topography presentation. By such set-up, a non-experienced is able to use the instrumentation in a more straight-forward manner, and the repeatability and reliability are increased [6].

3 Discussion and conclusions:

The need for standardized protocol for objective assessment based on the EMG measurements is not a novelty. BMCA (Brain Motor Control Assessment) study has already been proposed [8]. Nevertheless, the novelties induced by technological and processing improvements should be taken into account for future work. Author has a strong expectation that combination of various objective measurements presents a main future direction in assessment in neurorehabilitation: it can be related to assessment of various properties of muscle (e. g. combined measurement of ultrasound and electrical property of muscle) or it can be related to sensing variety of properties related to sensory-motor function (e. g. combined measurements of EMG and electroencephalography signals). Team work among clinicians, engineers, physicians, and others towards assessment advances is and will be the best direction to follow.

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PREGLED NOVIH METODA I INSTRUMENTACIJE ZA OCENU SENZORNO-MOTORNOG SISTEMA U REHABILITACIJI

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Sažetak: Ubrzani tehnološki napredak je uslovio i povećano interesovanje za razvoj novih rehabilitacionih procedura. Kako bi se dejstvo predloženih terapija optimizovalo i maksimiziralo, neophodno je da postoje odgovarajuće metode ocene oporavka. Ovaj rad je posvećen pregledu novih metoda u oceni senzorno-motorne funkcije pomoću elektromiografije. Nova instrumentacija, metode analize i protokoli su predstavljeni u ovom radu za ocenu voljne mišićne kontrakcije i evociranih potencijala. Glavni doprinosi u oceni oporavka kao što su mera kokontraksije za opis aktivacionog obrasca mišićnih grupa i primena matričnih elektroda za električnu stimulaciju i merenje evociranih potencijala su predstavljeni. Preporuke za dalje pravce razvoja i primene ovih procedura su date u poređenju sa već postojećim protokolima.

Ključne reči: evaluacija mišićne funkcije, polimiografija, evocirani potencijal, matrična elektroda, senzorno-motorni oporavak

Predavanje po pozivu

TRANSKRANIJALNA MAGNETNA STIMULACIJA U REHABILITACIJI

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Sažetak

Cilj neurorehabilitacije je razvijanje terapije koja se bazira na razumevanju funkcije mozga posle povrede i koja poboljšava ne samo bihevioralne i kognitivne funkcije, već i funkcije